

QUEDEE: Quest for Unrelenting Experimentation of Durable Electronic Editions

Van Zundert, Joris J.

joris.van.zundert@gmail.com

Huygens Institute – Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences, Niederlande

ORCID: 0000-0003-3862-7602

Despite decades of investment in digital infrastructure for scholarly editions, sustainability remains a significant and unresolved challenge. Scholarly digital editions and digital humanities research software show worryingly short lifespans and high obsolescence rates. A comprehensive analysis (Neuefeind et al. 2020) found that, of 466 tracked digital scholarly editions, 376 had disappeared. Digital editions have an average lifespan of 8.5 years (Helling, Schildkamp, and Mathiak 2019). Many projects vanish due to lapsing funding, institutional neglect, or loss of personnel, demonstrating that even robust initial infrastructure cannot guarantee long-term survival (Neuefeind et al. 2020). Technical and organizational vulnerabilities seriously jeopardize the longevity of digital scholarly editions. There is a large maintenance burden associated with ever-changing technologies and software frameworks. Keeping projects 'in sync' with evolving standards, platforms, and interfaces often outstrips the resources or expertise available to scholarly teams (Viglianti and del Rio Riande 2025; Boot and Zundert van 2011). It is questionable whether textual scholars possess, or even should possess, the skills needed to keep up with coding and digital infrastructural demands (Pierazzo 2019; Smithies et al. 2019). As a result, many digital editions become obsolete or unusable within a decade. Graphical interfaces are notoriously expensive in development and design effort, and may face obsolescence in a mere couple of years, while it is uncertain if they constitute much of the scholarly value (cf. Andrews and Van Zundert 2018 and Turska, Cummings, and Rahtz 2016 for various perspectives). Many digital editions rely on project-specific, often experimental, infrastructure, with insufficient planning for maintenance or handover. Institutional priorities, lack of comprehensive archiving strategies, and the disconnect between editorial teams and infrastructure providers exacerbate this problem, resulting in fragmented and underfunded infrastructure. Scholars have noted the "digital entropy" of scholarly resources, where, immediately after launch, the risk of abandonment and decay begins to increase (Viglianti and del Rio Riande 2025).

Thus sustainability and longevity of digital scholarly editions (and digital scholarly resources in a more generic sense) remain nagging headaches. Ironically in stark contrast to the physical historical documents that survive. Manuscripts over a thousand years old remain in libraries. Battered through time, natural disasters, and human violence surely, but often intact and readable. An estimated survival ratio of medieval works of heroic and chivalric fiction of 63.2 to 73.5% (Kestemont et al. 2022) suggests that physical written works boast excellent survivability. This, while the sustainability and longevity of digital information is staggeringly failing if indeed 80.7% of a set of digital editions disappears in merely 8.5 years (Helling, Schildkamp, and Mathiak 2019).

The "state of the art" sustainability for digital scholarly editions should have textual scholars, digital or not, running and screaming. However, mostly the textual scholarship community seems to have turned it into another locus of discourse. Most of that discourse suggests that digital durability is an infrastructural issue that must be addressed at process, community, or institutional level (cf. e.g. Edmond and Morselli 2020; Pierazzo 2019; Tucker 2022). The current mainstream solution to the problem is to promote FAIR principles (Tucker 2022) and data and software development good practices (The Endings Project Team 2023). However, all proposed solutions seemingly assume the unproblematic durable existence of digital infrastructure to carry data and software. Digital infrastructure organizations, such as TextGrid, CLARIAH, or academic cloud services, are axiomatic in these sustainability stories. Yet these infrastructures themselves are highly vulnerable (Eghbal 2016). They are dependent on extensive institutional resources, funding, and backing, all of which are rather more ephemeral and changeable than perpetual. As the Dutch Research Council (NWO) put it diplomatically: "Considering the long-term commitments that are required and the increasing number of research infrastructures, there is a need for well-advised and well-informed choices and decisions [...] to create a portfolio [...] that is financially sustainable" (Van den Berg et al. 2023).

Given the demonstrable vulnerability of digital data and infrastructure, warnings for a digital dark age (Jeffrey 2012; Ghosh 2015; Migowski 2016) are not to be ignored as merely luddite fear mongering. They are essential calls to action. Archiving digital born resources is an enormous challenge given the fleetingness of their existence (Nielsen 2016, Teszelsky 2019). Some theory exists (e.g. Del Turco 2022) on sustainability of digital editions, and there are venues that actively pursue improved sustainability of digital publications, for instance through "micro-editions" (cf. Baker and Tomasek 2022). However, mostly the problem of longevity of SDEs seems ignored by textual scholars. This while their preoccupation is the cultural memory and textual archive of humanity (McGann 2015), and while they are the foremost experts on the undisputed master of human culture information longevity: the book. It may be that book historians, textual scholars, and philologists have taken little research interest in this subject because they are so

used to the materiality of books that its durability transpires as a given that does not stand out. But arguably the book's specific materiality is exactly why it fulfills its task of remaining around so remarkably well. That durability is also a property any digital simulacrum is completely incapable of reproducing. The expected durability of pigment on paper is over 2,000 years, while digital durability is measured in years rather than in millennia (Bollacker 2010).

We argue that digital textual scholars should seriously address the durability and longevity issues of digital scholarly editions. This problem has received little attention. As iterated, the common assumption is that digital infrastructure will solve it. However, relying on future technology for solutions is questionable. Technical solutions require current research and development. Research must be argued, proposed, funded, and incited. Assuming some future magical solution undermines the urgency for needed research.

QUEDEE (pronounced somewhere between “Q.E.D” and “cutie”) is a long-term, extremely low-cost, maker/tinkerer oriented, awareness raising experiment to table and investigate the issue of durability of digital scholarly editions. QUEDEE is primarily driven by one research question: how can we create a digital scholarly edition that might possibly rival the durability exhibited by print based book editions?

As far as we can see, little has been proposed concretely by way of an answer in the history of digital scholarly editing. Publications usually address the problem in theoretical fashion, arguing for minimal computing and self-contained web technology-based editions that only apply widely baseline available standards such as HTML, CSS, and JavaScript (Holmes and Takeda 2018, Viglianti and del Rio Riande 2025; Wikle and Williamson 2025; Moran 2025). An open standards based, static webpages approach to publishing digital scholarly editions is from the perspective of sustainability an obvious good practice which QUEDEE will follow. Apart from few and scant projects of the Minimal Computing working group (GO::DH Minimal Computing Working Group 2015) not many tangible hardware-oriented results have come forth with respect to self-contained technology for digital scholarly editions. Bainbridge et al. (2008) realized a digital library hosted on an Apple iPod music player, that could however not be maintained due to Apple's proprietary policies. The scantness of experiments in our view stands in painful contrast to the values that minimal computing based scholarly editions could bring to the field and wider communities (Risam and Gil 2022, Viglianti et al. 2022).

Given the problems of sustainability of institutional digital infrastructure for QUEDEE we assert that any solution for durable digital scholarly editions must be self-contained. The self-contained nature is also motivated by the requirement that we want our solution to mimic as much as possible all physical features of the book, as that is our lead example for durability. Therefore, all hardware should be self-contained, self-reliant, portable, and should ideally in physical dimensions not much surpass those of an average book. Furthermore, we consider ourselves to be held to all the principles that are generally now considered as

good practices for the sustainability of data and software, to wit those manifested by The Endings Project (2023). These principles include (but are not limited to) the use of only open standards for data, extensive documentation, continuous integration and version management, independence of server-side software, non-usage of web development frameworks or fashionable but short-lived software libraries, massive redundancy, and graceful failure.

QUEDEE is currently moving from its design phase into a first implementation phase. The design (cf. also figure 1) proposes a Raspberry Pi 4 platform as the hardware backbone, as this is well documented and open technology (Allan 2012). Arguably Arduino or Raspberry Pi ZeroW might have represented even more minimalist technical or financial choices. However, these platforms are somewhat less fit for our minimal software development and screen estate requirements. QUEDEE will furnish a 480 by 320 pixel touchscreen and will run Raspberry Pi OS “Bookworm”, the latest version of the Raspberry Pi operating system, based on Debian 12 (“Documentation” 2025). The OS runs a NGINX lightweight web server (Young 2024) which on boot will present a HTML/JavaScript based scholarly digital edition of “Van den Vos Reynaerde” (Bouwman and Besamusca 2009) in Chromium (Li et al. 2025). The Raspberry Pi is configured to start an open stand-alone Wifi network, so other devices may connect and browse the scholarly edition independent of the provided touchscreen. These choices guarantee a well-documented lightweight open-source software stack. Although all software will be archived in an online repository, the idea is that once installed neither hardware nor software will change. As long as hardware and software remain uncorrupted this warrants proper execution. The device is encased in a cover box that is strongly reminiscent of a book, in accordance with the idea of mimicking a print publication. The cover box will also contain a manual on the setup and use of the system, as well as an explanation of the why and how of the device and project.

The strategy for guaranteeing longevity of the design is based on redundancy and graceful fallbacks. The touchscreen and Wifi network capabilities serve as each other's fallback. Because the storage medium of a Raspberry Pi is an SSD card, a few copies of that card are provided in the box cover. We assume that the scholarly edition and hardware must also run in case there is no power source, for which we include two solar panels. A solar power manager module must be included to stabilize power supply. All documentation and data are redundantly stored on the device itself in plain text formats. Lastly two stacks of minified facsimiles of the scholarly edition and its primary source are provided as last resort fallbacks in case none of the hardware, software, or data turns out to be salvageable in the long term.

Fig. 1: Conceptual design of QUEDEE kit and its components.

To test the durability of the design, collaboration with the Dutch National Library will be sought to store the book-like case and the contained elements in realistic long-term archival conditions. The proposed test trajectory consists of retrieving the device from the National Library's depot in 1, 2, 5, and 10 years. Each time the functioning of the device and fallbacks will be evaluated, and results (as well as potentially intervening technological developments) will be published in follow up papers.

The current design has known flaws. For instance, the Raspberry Pi platform relies on SSD memory, which is demonstrably susceptible to deterioration of the digital information contained. Reliable retainment of information for such cards, anecdotally, varies between a few years and more than a decade, where the value of "more than" is unfortunately unknown. Another clearly suboptimal feature are the batteries enabling the solar power management module. Because the chemical compounds of batteries are an obvious threat to holdings, no library will accept batteries as part of keeping and safeguarding any book. This problem may be less inhibiting however, because it is reasonable to assume that any future user that is able to understand the intended operation of the device, will also be able to provide or even manufacture a sufficient battery.

These a priori design flaws in our view do not invalidate the project. They rather serve as a reminder of how hard and difficult the task is that we propose here. This paper therefore, is not so much a final report as it is a proposed point of departure for an urgently needed discussion on a sincerely neglected issue in digital textual scholarship –i.e. the problematic longevity of digital scholarly editions. It also serves as a genuine RFC (Request for Comments) on how the design of the durable digital scholarly edition and the project may be improved.

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